

Computation of Novel Binomial Series and Theorems using Bivariable Geometric Series based on Algebraic Expression

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Abstract: Nowadays, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. In this paper, the author introduces a novel binomial series and its theorems using bivariable geometric series based on algebraic expression. This computing technique can enable the researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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1. Introduction

Geometric series [1,11] played a vital role in differential and integral calculus at the earlier stage of development and still continues as an important part of the study in science, engineering, management and its applications [12]. In this article, a new binomial series without binomial coefficients are computed with binomial theorems.

2. Novel Binomial Series

Before introducing novel binomial series and its theorems, let us prove the sum of geometric series based on algebraic expression.

$$x^{n+1} = x^{n+1} \Rightarrow x^{n+1} = (x-1)x^n + x^n.$$

We can expand the above expression further as follows:

$$x^{n+1} = (x-1)x^n + (x-1)x^{n-1} + (x-1)x^{n-2} + \dots + (x-1)x^1 + (x-1)x^0 + x^0.$$

$$(x-1)(x^n + x^{n-1} + x^{n-2} + x^{n-3} + \dots + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1) = x^{n+1} - 1.$$

Now, we can show the geometric series using the above algebraic expression.

$$1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots + x^{n-2} + x^{n-1} + x^n = \frac{x^{n+1} - 1}{x - 1} \Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^n x^k = \frac{x^{n+1} - 1}{x - 1}, x \neq 1.$$

Next, the author of this article introduces a new binomial series using the above geometric series.

Theorem 2.1: $\sum_{k=0}^n x^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n x^{n-k} y^k = \frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x - y} = \frac{y^{n+1} - x^{n+1}}{y - x}, x \neq y.$

Proof. Let's prove this theorem using the geometric series as follows.

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^k = \frac{\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^{n+1} - 1}{\frac{x}{y} - 1} = \left(\frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{y^{n+1}}\right) \left(\frac{y}{x - y}\right), x \neq y. \quad (1)$$

By simplifying the equation (1), we get

$$y^n \left(1 + \frac{x}{y} + \frac{x^2}{y^2} + \frac{x^3}{y^3} + \dots + \frac{x^{n-1}}{y^{n-1}} + \frac{x^n}{y^n} \right) = \frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x - y}, x \neq y.$$

$$y^n + xy^{n-1} + x^2y^{n-2} + x^3y^{n-3} + \dots + x^{n-1}y + x^n = \frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x - y}, x \neq y.$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n x^k y^{n-k} = \frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x - y}, x \neq y. \quad (2)$$

By rearranging the binomial series (2), we obtain

$$\sum_{k=0}^n x^{n-k} y^k = \frac{y^{n+1} - x^{n+1}}{y - x}, x \neq y. \quad (3)$$

From the binomial series (2) and (3), we conclude that

$$\sum_{k=0}^n x^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n x^{n-k} y^k = \frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x - y} = \frac{y^{n+1} - x^{n+1}}{y - x}, x \neq y. \quad (4)$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Corollary 2.1: $\sum_{k=0}^n x^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n x^{n-k} y^k = (n+1)x^n, \quad \text{for } x = y.$

Corollary 2.2: $\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} x^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} x^{n-k} y^k = \frac{x^n y - x y^n}{x - y} = \frac{x y^n - x^n y}{y - x}, x \neq y.$

Let's prove the corollary 2.2 as follows:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n x^{n-k} y^k = x^n + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} x^{n-k} y^k + y^n = \frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x - y}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} x^{n-k} y^k = \frac{x^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x - y} - (x^n + y^n) = \frac{x^n y - x y^n}{x - y}$$

$$\therefore \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} x^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} x^{n-k} y^k = \frac{x^n y - x y^n}{x - y} = \frac{x y^n - x^n y}{y - x}, x \neq y.$$

Theorem 2.2: $\sum_{i=k}^n x^i y^{n-i} = \sum_{i=k}^n x^{n-i} y^i = \frac{x^{n+1} - x^k y^{n+1-k}}{x - y} = \frac{y^{n+1} - y^k x^{n+1-k}}{y - x}, x \neq y.$

Proof. Let's prove the theorem using the geometric series with rational numbers.

$$\sum_{i=k}^n \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^i = \frac{\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^{n+1} - \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^k}{\frac{x}{y} - 1} = \left(\frac{x^{n+1}}{y^{n+1}} - x^k y^{-k}\right) \left(\frac{y}{x - y}\right) = \frac{1}{y^n} \left(\frac{x^{n+1} - x^k y^{n+1-k}}{x - y}\right).$$

$$y^n \sum_{i=k}^n \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^i = \sum_{i=k}^n x^i y^{n-i} = \frac{x^{n+1} - x^k y^{n+1-k}}{x-y} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=k}^n x^{n-i} y^i = \frac{y^{n+1} - y^k x^{n+1-k}}{y-x}.$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=k}^n x^i y^{n-i} = \sum_{i=k}^n x^{n-i} y^i = \frac{x^{n+1} - x^k y^{n+1-k}}{x-y} = \frac{y^{n+1} - y^k x^{n+1-k}}{y-x}, x \neq y.$$

Corollary 2.3: $\sum_{i=k}^n x^i y^{n-i} = \sum_{i=k}^n x^{n-k} y^k = (n+1-k)x^n, \quad \text{for } x = y.$

Corollary 2.4(i): $\sum_{k=0}^n (x+y)^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n y^k (x+y)^{n-k} = \frac{(x+y)^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x}, x \neq 0.$

Let us prove the corollary 2.4(i) as follows:

Case(i): $\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\frac{x+y}{y}\right)^k = \frac{\left(\frac{x+y}{y}\right)^{n+1} - 1}{\frac{x+y}{y} - 1} \Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^n (x+y)^k y^{n-k} = \frac{(x+y)^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x}, x \neq 0.$

Case(ii): $\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\frac{y}{x+y}\right)^k = \frac{\left(\frac{y}{x+y}\right)^{n+1} - 1}{\frac{y}{x+y} - 1} \Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^n (x+y)^k y^{n-k} = \frac{(x+y)^{n+1} - y^{n+1}}{x}, x \neq 0.$

Hence proved.

Example: If $x = 1$ and $y = 1$, then $\sum_{k=0}^n 3^k 2^{n-k} = 3^{n+1} - 2^{n+1}.$

Corollary 2.4(ii): $\sum_{k=0}^n x^k (x+y)^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n (x+y)^k x^{n-k} = \frac{(x+y)^{n+1} - x^{n+1}}{y}, y \neq 0$

Example: If $x = 1$ and $y = 1$, then $\sum_{k=0}^n 2^k = 2^{n+1} - 1.$

Corollary 2.5(i): $\sum_{k=0}^n (x-y)^k x^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n x^k (x-y)^{n-k} = \frac{x^{n+1} - (x-y)^{n+1}}{y}, x \neq 0.$

Let us prove the corollary 2.5(i) as follows:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\frac{x-y}{x}\right)^k = \frac{\left(\frac{x-y}{x}\right)^{n+1} - 1}{\frac{x-y}{x} - 1} \Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^n (x-y)^k x^{n-k} = \frac{x^{n+1} - (x-y)^{n+1}}{y}, x \neq 0.$$

Hence proved.

Corollary 2.5(ii):
$$\sum_{k=0}^n (y-x)^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n y^k (y-x)^{n-k} = \frac{y^{n+1} - (y-x)^{n+1}}{x}, x \neq 0.$$

Let us prove the corollary 2.5(ii) as follows:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\frac{x-y}{-y}\right)^k = \sum_{k=0}^n \left(\frac{y-x}{y}\right)^k = \frac{\left(\frac{y-x}{y}\right)^{n+1} - 1}{\frac{y-x}{y} - 1} \Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^n (x-y)^k x^{n-k} = \frac{y^{n+1} - (y-x)^{n+1}}{x}.$$

Hence proved.

Theorem 2.3:
$$\prod_{k=0}^n (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) = \frac{x^{2^{n+1}} - y^{2^{n+1}}}{x - y}, x \neq y.$$

Proof. Let's prove this theorem as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x^2 - y^2}{x - y} &= \frac{(x+y)(x-y)}{x-y} = x + y. \\ \frac{x^{2^2} - y^{2^2}}{x - y} &= \frac{x^4 - y^4}{x - y} = \frac{(x^2 + y^2)(x^2 - y^2)}{x - y} = (x^2 + y^2)(x + y). \\ \frac{x^{2^3} - y^{2^3}}{x - y} &= \frac{x^8 - y^8}{x - y} = (x^4 + y^4)(x^2 + y^2)(x + y) = (x^{2^2} + y^{2^2})(x^{2^1} + y^{2^1})(x^{2^0} + y^{2^0}). \end{aligned}$$

We can continue the same process up to 2^{n+1} .

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x^{2^3} - y^{2^3}}{x - y} &= \frac{x^8 - y^8}{x - y} = (x^{2^n} + y^{2^n})(x^{2^{n-1}} + y^{2^{n-1}}) \dots (x^{2^1} + y^{2^1})(x^{2^0} + y^{2^0}). \\ \therefore \prod_{k=0}^n (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) &= \frac{x^{2^{n+1}} - y^{2^{n+1}}}{x - y}, x \neq y. \end{aligned}$$

Hence proved.

Corollary 2.6:
$$\prod_{k=0}^{n-1} x^{2^k} = x^{2^n - 1}.$$

Case i: Let's prove the corollary 2.6 using the theorem 2.3.

$$\prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x^{2^k} + 0^{2^k}) = \frac{x^{2^n} - 0}{x - 0} \Rightarrow \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} x^{2^k} = \frac{x^{2^n}}{x} = x^{2^n - 1}.$$

Case II: Let's prove the corollary 2.6 using the geometric series.

$$\prod_{k=0}^{n-1} x^{2^k} = x^1 \times x^2 \times x^{2^2} \times x^{2^3} \times \dots \times x^{2^{n-1}} = x^{1+2+2^2+2^3+\dots+2^{n-1}} = x^{\frac{2^n-1}{2-1}} = x^{2^n-1}.$$

Hence proved.

Corollary 2.7: If $x = y$, then
$$\prod_{k=0}^n (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) = 2 \prod_{k=0}^n x^{2^k} = 2x^{2^n - 1}.$$

Corollary 2.8:
$$\sum_{i=0}^{2^{n+1}-1} x^i y^{n-i} = \prod_{k=0}^n (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) = \frac{x^{2^{n+1}} - y^{2^{n+1}}}{x - y}, x \neq y.$$

Examples for corollary 2.8:

(i). Let $n = 0$.

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2^{0+1}-1} x^i y^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^{2-1} x^i y^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^1 x^i y^{n-i} = x + y = \frac{x^2 - y^2}{x - y}.$$

$$\prod_{k=0}^0 (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) = x + y = \frac{x^2 - y^2}{x - y}. \quad \therefore \sum_{i=0}^{2^{0+1}-1} x^i y^{n-i} = \prod_{k=0}^0 (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) = \frac{x^2 - y^2}{x - y}.$$

(ii). Let $n = 1$.

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2^{1+1}-1} x^i y^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^3 x^i y^{n-i} = x^3 + x^2 y + x y^2 + y^3 = \frac{x^{2^2} - y^{2^2}}{x - y} = \frac{x^4 - y^4}{x - y}.$$

$$\prod_{k=0}^1 (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) = (x + y)(x^2 + y^2) = x^3 + x^2 y + x y^2 + y^3 = \frac{x^4 - y^4}{x - y}.$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=0}^{2^{1+1}-1} x^i y^{n-i} = \prod_{k=0}^1 (x^{2^k} + y^{2^k}) = \frac{x^{2^2} - y^{2^2}}{x - y} = \frac{x^4 - y^4}{x - y}.$$

Corollary 2.9(i):
$$\sum_{k=0}^n (x + y)^k (x - y)^{n-k} = \frac{(x + y)^{n+1} - (x - y)^{n+1}}{2y}, x \neq 0.$$

Corollary 2.9(ii):
$$\sum_{k=0}^n (y + x)^k (y - x)^{n-k} = \frac{(y + x)^{n+1} - (y - x)^{n+1}}{2x}, x \neq 0.$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, a novel binomial series and theorems have been introduced for mathematical and computational application. This idea can enable the researchers for further involvement in the scientific research.

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